

Preparation and Use of Membrane Electrodes of Basic Salts of Deaminated Proteins for Determination of Cation Activities of Electrolytic Solutions. Part I. Deaminated Ovalbumin

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Film membranes (0.44 to 1.26 mm thick) of sodium salt of deaminated and denatured ovalbumin have been used for determining the membrane potential, using S.C.E. In case of NaCl solution with ionic strength ratio of 2 at the same pH on the two sides, the membrane potential is found to be nearly the same at different pH values of 4.0 to 7.5.

Na⁺ ion of the membrane could be exchanged for any other monovalent or divalent cation by placing the membrane in 1*N* solution of the respective electrolyte for 48 hr. Then after washing the membrane with distilled water, it could be used for determining activities of cations in the solutions of the corresponding salts at different concentrations in the range of 0.0015 to 0.025 *M* with molarity ratio of 2.0 in the case of monovalent cations. In the case of divalent cations, the concentration range is 0.00075 to 0.0186 with molarity ratio of 3.

Thin and uniform film membranes, prepared from natural and synthetic ion-exchangers, have been greatly used as membrane electrodes for the measurement of ionic activities by several workers¹⁻⁸. Membranes prepared from synthetic ampholytes by Jacobson⁹, containing weakly acidic and basic groups, were found to change charge density and polarity with pH.

The object of the present work was to prepare film membranes from the basic salts of deaminated and denatured ovalbumin, which were expected to work as non-ampholytes and insoluble cation-exchangers, and use them for determining cation activity of solutions from membrane potential (ψ). The denatured and deaminated ovalbumin contains free -COOH groups, H of which can be replaced by any metal ion. Besides this, on account of the presence of polar groups, it was found to swell to a slight extent, making it elastic and ionisable.

In the present investigation, thin films of Na⁺, K⁺, Li⁺, Ca²⁺, Ba²⁺, and Mg²⁺ salts of the deaminated and denatured ovalbumin were used as membrane electrodes at 25°.

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2. Marshall, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1939, **43**, 1155; 1941, **45**, 1911; 1944, **48**, 67.
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6. Sinha, this *Journal*, 1953, **30**, 529; 1954, **31**, 577.
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9. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 570.

EXPERIMENTAL

Crystalline isoelectric ovalbumin was prepared from the white of fresh hen's eggs according to Keckwick and Cannon¹⁰. The crystalline isoelectric ovalbumin (ca. 20 g.) was then denatured and washed with acetone till free of Na_2SO_4 . This was deaminated using HNO_2 (prepared with NaNO_2 -AcOH at pH 4) by the method suggested by Philpot and Small¹¹. On deamination, protein $-\text{NH}_2$ group was modified to protein $-\text{OH}$. Thus the ampholytic nature of the protein was destroyed, as tested by finding the ψ at various pHs, as shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Effect of pH on the membrane potential of the sodium salt of deaminated and denatured ovalbumin.

Thickness of the film = 0.82 mm.

Molarity ratio of Na^+ Cl^-		pH.	$\psi_{\text{obs.}}$	Molarity ratio of Na^+ Cl^-		pH.	$\psi_{\text{obs.}}$
2.00	2.25	4.0	17.40 mv	2.02	2.25	6.0	16.90 mv
2.00	2.25	4.5	17.55	2.04	2.25	6.5	16.60
2.00	2.25	5.0	17.55	2.05	2.25	7.0	16.40
2.00	2.25	5.5	17.20	2.08	2.25	7.5	16.20

The semi-dry powder of the deaminated ovalbumin (denatured) was kept between filter paper pads and pressed into films by applying uniform pressure in the screw press for 48 hr. Thus yellowish film membranes of thickness varying from 0.44 to 1.25 mm could be prepared. The films were converted into Na-form by treating them with $N/10$ -NaCl, brought to pH 8 with NaHCO_3 .

The films, semidried in a vacuum desiccator, were cut into small circular discs (about 1.5 cm in diameter) and were soaked in water for about 2 hr. for swelling. The electrical resistance of the swollen film (0.55 mm thick), immersed in 0.1N-KCl, was found to be 127 ohms. The films could be fixed to one of the ends of a pyrex glass tube (dia. 1.5 cm) between two rubber washers on which a waxed metal cap could be screwed up. Only those films, which showed zero or negligible asymmetric potential, were used in the experiments.

For the determination of ψ , two small dip-type saturated calomel electrodes of exactly the same electrode potential were introduced in the solutions of different concentrations on the two sides of the membrane. Cambridge box potentiometer, reading to 0.01mv, was used in combination with a ballistic mirror galvanometer as the null point instrument. The dilute solution was always connected to the positive terminal of the potentiometer.

For studying the effect of pH on ψ of the deaminated ovalbumin, the solutions used on the two sides of the membrane were 0.01 and 0.02M-NaCl, buffered with acetate buffer (pH 4.0 to 5.5) and with phosphate buffer (pH 6.0 to 7.5); first solutions of 0.2 and 0.1 ionic strength were prepared by adding the appropriate quantity of the NaCl to these buffers, according to Conway¹²

10. *Biochem. J.*, 1936, **30**, 232.

11. *Ibid.*, 1938, **32**, 542.

12. "Electro-Chemical Data", Elsevier Publishing, New York, 1952.

For determining activities of various cations, the Na^+ ion of the membrane was exchanged for other monovalent or divalent cation by placing the film membrane in 1*N* solution of the respective electrolyte for 48 hr. The conditioning period was sometimes more than 48 hr. for bringing the membrane in the required cationic form, as tested from the constancy of the membrane potential.

Values of ψ , measured and calculated in the case of solutions of various cations at various activities, and different ratios are shown in Table II. The cation activities were obtained by multiplying molarity with activity coefficient of the ion, calculated by graphical method, plotting the known values from Conway's electrochemical data¹².

TABLE II

Molarity, cation activity, and membrane potential of diff. salt solutions.

1. Electrolyte. 2. Film thickness.	Molarity.		Cation activity.		Membrane potential.	
	Inside.	Outside.	Inside.	Outside.	Obs.	Calc.
1. LiCl	0.0031	0.0015	0.00207	0.00145	18.35 mv	18.31 mv
2. 1.25 mm	0.0002	0.0031	0.00584	0.00297	17.45	17.35
	0.0125	0.0062	0.01146	0.00584	17.10	17.27
	0.0250	0.0125	0.02240	0.01146	17.06	17.17
	0.0500	0.0250	0.04350	0.02240	14.00	17.01
1. NaCl	0.0031	0.0015	0.00207	0.00146	18.20	18.22
2. 1.17 mm	0.0002	0.0031	0.00585	0.00297	17.60	17.36
	0.0125	0.0062	0.01147	0.00585	17.30	17.24
	0.0250	0.0125	0.02240	0.01147	17.01	17.15
	0.0500	0.0250	0.04300	0.02240	10.05	16.72
1. MgCl_2	0.0022	0.0007	0.00178	0.00065	13.15	12.90
2. 0.53 mm	0.0045	0.0015	0.00320	0.00123	12.85	12.59
	0.0093	0.0031	0.00818	0.00234	12.20	12.44
	0.0186	0.0062	0.01293	0.00434	12.05	11.83
	0.0375	0.0125	0.02393	0.00791	9.10	11.18
1. CaCl_2	0.0022	0.0007	0.00176	0.00064	12.70	12.99
2. 0.67 mm	0.0045	0.0015	0.00323	0.00122	12.25	12.40
	0.0093	0.0031	0.00598	0.00234	12.12	12.02
	0.0186	0.0062	0.01243	0.00423	11.20	11.57
	0.0375	0.0125	0.02331	0.00766	4.00	11.16

N. B. The membrane potentials obtained for KCl were nearly the same as NaCl and those for BaCl_2 , same as CaCl_2 .

DISCUSSION

The deaminated protein film has been observed to swell to the desired extent in presence of dilute solutions of various monovalent and divalent salts; due to the presence of sufficient free water inside, it is able to ionise. Besides this, there is no influence of the thickness of the film membrane within the range 0.44 to 1.25 mm on membrane potential. The membranes were quite elastic and could be preserved in water containing a crystal of thymol. ψ of the film formed from untreated, denatured ovalbumin varied with pH, being negative below isoelectric point (pH 5.2), at which it is zero and positive above it up to pH 7.5; above pH 8, it was soluble.

Table I shows that ψ of the film, formed from Na salt of deaminated, denatured ovalbumin, is nearly constant in case of NaCl solutions of ionic strengths 0.01 and 0.02 at the same pH in presence of acetate buffers for pH 4.0 to 5.5 and phosphate buffers for pH 6.0 to 7.5. The slight variation may be due to influence of pH on swelling of the membrane and consequent variation in ionisation of the membrane due to change in amount of free water; since the pH and the concentration of the buffer solutions on both sides are the same, there is no possibility of bi-ionic potential, as suggested by Jacobson⁹. This shows that the deamination of the denatured ovalbumin is almost complete and it is no more an ampholyte since in the case of a synthetic polyampholyte, membrane potential varies with pH of solutions, as observed by Jacobson⁹. So the sodium salt of the deaminated protein (R-COONa) becomes prominently cation exchanging and the membrane is able to maintain almost the same amount of -ve charge between pH 4.0 and 7.5. So a basic salt of deaminated, denatured ovalbumin could be used for the determination of cation activities of electrolytic solutions. It was experimentally determined that Na^+ ion of the membrane could be exchanged with other monovalent or divalent cation, on being kept in contact with 1*N* solution of the respective salt for more than 48 hr.

Table II shows the membrane potentials obtained with film membranes (0.44 to 1.25 mm thick) of the respective basic salts of deaminated, denatured ovalbumin as the membrane electrodes in case of solutions of different concentrations and molarity ratios. The equilibrium membrane potential reached within 15 minutes and remained constant for more than half an hour. In case of aqueous solutions of NaCl, LiCl, and KCl, the observed membrane potentials are in good agreement with those calculated at 25° from the Nernst equation:

$$E = 0.059 \log_{10} \frac{a_2}{a_1} .$$

Within the experimental error of $\pm 2.5\%$ in membrane potential with molarity ratio 2:1, the valid range of concentration for monovalent cations is between 0.0015 *M* and 0.025 *M*. When the ratio is 3:1, for divalent cations like Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , and Ba^{2+} , the valid range of concentration is 0.00075 *M* to 0.0186 *M* and the error in membrane potential is comparatively small, ranging from 0.4 to $\pm 2.5\%$. The low valid range of concentration in the case of divalent cations is ascribed to less ionisation of the basic salts of the protein when compared to those of monovalent cations.